

Table 1: Research studies that have examined Australian opinions towards marijuana (1985 to 2020)

Name/Publication	Source	Year	Author	Sample and Method	Focus/Questions	Key Findings
National Drug Strategy Household Survey (NDSHS) (otherwise known as the <i>Social Issues in Australia Survey</i> in 1985, and the <i>National Campaign against Drug Abuse Social Issues Survey from 1988-1993</i>)	AIHW	2019, 2016, 2013, 2010, 2007, 2004, 2001, 1998, 1995, 1993, 1991, 1988, 1985	Department of Health, Housing and Community Services (1985-1991), Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (1993 – present)	2019 N=22000 (TBA Q3 2020) 2016 N=23772 2013 N=23855 2010 N=26648 2007 N=23356 2004 N=29445 2001 N=26744 1998 N=10340 1995 N=3850 1993 N=3500 1991 N=2850 1988 N=2257 1985 N=2791 Non-institutionalised Australian population, aged 14 and over (also included 12 and 13 year olds from 2004) Stratified multi-stage sample, by geographic location Survey method: 1985-1995: Face to face interview 1998: Face to face interview/Self administered questionnaire 2001: Face to face interview/Self administered questionnaire/Telephone 2004, 2007: Self administered questionnaire (85% in 2007)/Telephone (15% in 2007) 2010: drop and collect method 2013: 2016: Self administered questionnaire/Telephone 2019: Self administered questionnaire, online and over the phone Response rates 2019: TBA Q3 2020 2016: 51.1% 2013: 49.1% 2010: 50.6% 2007: 49.3% 2004: 45.6% 2001: 50% 1998: 56% 1985-1995: Not known	Survey contains questions on: Perceptions of the drug problem and drug harms; Extent of approval for drug use; Approval for various policy options; Legal status of drugs Covers all drug types, licit and illicit. Some of the questions and question wording have changed over time. For a full list of questions, see 2019 NDSHS questionnaire	
Australian secondary school students alcohol and drug (ASSAD) survey	ASSDA	2020, 2017, 2014, 2011, 2008, 2005, 2002, 1999, 1996, 1993, 1990, 1987, 1984		2020 N= (TBA) 2017 2014 2011 2008 2005 2002 1999 1996 1993 1990 1987 1984 Australian secondary school students, aged between 12 and 17 Paper-based surveys administered in secondary schools	Use of tobacco and alcohol among Australian adolescent students since 1984, and the use of other substances since 1996	
Australian Election Study	ASSDA	2007, 2004, 2001, 1998, 1996, 1993, 1990	Australian National University	2007 N=1829 2004 N=1714 2001 N=1967 1998 N=1833 1996 N=1775 1993 N=2135 1990 N=2012 Australian population Stratified systematic random sample Self administered questionnaire (mailed) Response rates not known	<i>The smoking of marijuana should NOT be a criminal offence:</i> Strongly agree Agree Neither agree nor disagree Disagree Strongly disagree	
Australian Survey of Social Attitudes	ASSDA	2003, 2005, 2007	Australian National University	2003, 2005 N=4000 2007 N=8000 Australian population Random sample – stratified by state Self administered questionnaire (mailed) Response rates not known	<i>The smoking of marijuana should not be a criminal offence:</i> Strongly Agree Agree Neither Agree nor disagree Disagree Strongly Disagree Can't choose	
National Social Science Survey (NSSS)	ASSDA	1986-7, 1987-8, 1989-90	Australian National University	1986-7 N=1528 1987-8 N=1663 1989-90 N=6136 Australian population Self administered questionnaire (mailed) Response rates not known	1986-7: <i>Legalising the use of marijuana – are you in favour?</i> Yes!! Yes ?? No No!! 1987-8: <i>Legalising the use of marijuana -- are you in favour?</i> Very Yes Yes ?? No Very No 1989-90:	

					<p><i>Legalising the use of marijuana -- are you in favour?</i> <i>Strongly in favour</i> <i>In favour</i> <i>Neither</i> <i>Opposed</i> <i>Strongly Opposed</i></p>	
Roy Morgan Single Source Australia (otherwise known as <i>Roy Morgan Update</i>)	Roy Morgan	1977-2001, 2014-19	Roy Morgan	<p>1977-01: Not known 2014-15, N=15867 2018-19, N=14383</p> <p>Establishment Survey (ES) N=50000 Self-Completion Material (SCM) N=20000</p> <p>Australian population aged 14 and over from private households</p> <p>Individual selection – youngest person at home</p> <p>Random starting addresses – up to 3 calls to establish contact (different times)</p> <p>Clusters of 8 interviews – 1 interview per household</p> <p>Boosted sampling for selected areas. Weekly and monthly reports on sample performance. Weighted monthly by Area, Age, Sex, Household size (Source: ABS)</p> <p>Survey method: Face to face in people's homes using computer assisted personal interviewing (CAPI) / Telephone in people's homes using computer assisted telephone interviewing (CATI); and Self-Completion Material (SCM) placed by interviewer after Establishment Survey Interview</p> <p>Response rates: CAPI: 1 in 3 effective contacts results in an interview CATI: 1 in 5 effective contacts results in an interview</p> <p>Establishment interview matched to returned Self-Completion questionnaires</p>	<p><i>In your opinion, should the smoking of marijuana be made legal – or should it remain illegal?</i> <i>Legal</i> <i>Illegal</i> <i>Don't know</i></p> <p>Establishment Survey (ES)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newspaper Readership • Magazine Readership • Cinema Attendance • TV Viewing • Radio Listening • Financial Institutions • Telecommunications • Credit Cards • Loans • Accounts • Business Decisions • Demographics • Roy Morgan Values Segments <p>Self-Completion Material (SCM)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activities and Interests • Alcoholic Beverages • Attitudes and Lifestyles • Catalogues • Food Purchases / Consumption • Gambling and Gaming • Holidays and Travel • Household Items / Appliances • Household Products Bought • Internet Behaviour and Preferences • Job Satisfaction • Location TV • Media Most Useful • Media Preference by Daypart • Media Usage • Motor Vehicles • Non-Alcoholic Beverages • Pay TV Channel Involvement • Personal Services • Radio Diary • Retail – Non-food Purchasing • Sectional Reading • Shares • Shopping Centres • Sporting Participation • Supermarkets • Take Away Food • Time Spent on Activities • Time Spent with Media • TV Attention Level • TV Diary • TV Program Involvement • Utilities • Website Visitation • Word of Mouth 	
Australia Talks National Survey				<p>N=54,000</p> <p>Australian population, stratified by geographic location</p>		<p>54% of Australians think marijuana should be legalised. The ACT has one of the country's lowest proportion of residents in favour (49 per cent) despite its reform agenda. Tasmania is most supportive with 56 per cent of residents in favour of legalisation.</p>
Illicit Drug Reporting System (IDRS) Interviews			NDARC	<p>Australian population N= ACT population N= NT population N= NSW population N= SA population N= TAS population N= QLD population N= VIC population N= WA population N=</p>	<p>Reports on national and jurisdictional drug trends</p>	
Ecstasy and Related Drugs Reporting System (EDRS) Interviews				<p>Australian population N= ACT population N= NT population N= NSW population N= SA population N= TAS population N= QLD population N= VIC population N= WA population N=</p>	<p>Reports on national and jurisdictional drug trends</p>	
Community attitudes towards cannabis law and the proposed Cannabis Infringement Notice scheme in Western Australia		2002, 2007	James Fetherston, Simon Lenton	<p>2002 N=809 2007 N=814</p> <p>Western Australian population</p> <p>Stratified sample to city/country (Ratio 75:25)</p> <p>Telephone Survey</p> <p>Response rates: 2002: 27.6% 2007: 38.1%</p> <p>Data weighting for age was trialled but found to have negligible effect on results</p>	<p><i>It should be legal for people over 18 to use cannabis:</i> <i>Strongly agree</i> <i>Agree somewhat</i> <i>Neither agree nor disagree</i> <i>Disagree somewhat</i> <i>Strongly disagree</i> <i>Don't know/refused to answer</i></p> <p><i>In general, do you think these new cannabis laws seem:</i> <i>A good idea</i> <i>A bad idea</i> <i>Unsure</i> <i>Refused to answer</i></p>	
Public perceptions of drugs causing most deaths in Australia 1986-93		1986, 1993	Ron Borland, Ngaire Donaghue, David Hill	<p>1986 N=1213 1993 N=1268</p> <p>Australian population</p> <p>Cluster sample from areas randomly selected from Australian electorates</p> <p>Face to face interviews</p> <p>Response rate not known</p> <p>Data weighted to age and gender distribution</p>	<p><i>Which drugs cause the most deaths in Australia?</i> <i>Open ended response</i></p>	
Public awareness, knowledge and attitudes regarding the CEN system in South		1997	Penny Heale, David Hawks,	<p>N=605</p>	<p><i>Should: Possession of <100g/Grow three plants/Grow 15 plants/Sell</i></p>	

Australia			Simon Lenton	South Australian population Random sample. Stratified by age (14-70) and place of residence (metro/non-metro). Quotas on age groups. Telephone survey Response rate: 89% [N=5527 telephone numbers randomly selected, N=675 contact made and eligible, N=605 completed survey]	25g for profit/Possession by a juvenile/Cannabis use for medical purposes/Give cannabis to friend or acquaintance/Driving while affected by cannabis be: Legal Illegal Don't know If illegal or don't know, should: Possession of <100g/Grow three plants/Grow 15 plants/Sell 25g for profit/Possession by a juvenile/Cannabis use for medical purposes/Give cannabis to friend or acquaintance/Driving while affected by cannabis be: Legal Criminal Non-criminal Don't know	
Public perceptions of the health and psychological consequences of cannabis use		1995	Wayne Hall, Joan Nelson	N=3264 Australian population Stratified – at least 400 per state/territory Telephone survey Response rate: 16%	From a health angle do you think regular use by an adult is OK? (i.e. once per week, once per fortnight) Yes No Don't know	
Pfizer Health Report		2006	Stollznow Research/NDARC	N=1439 Aged 18 and over Panel of 1000 Australian households. Sample adjusted by age and residential location. Telephone survey Response rate not known	From a health angle do you think regular use by an adult (18 years and over) is OK? (i.e. once a week or more)? Yes No Don't know I do not wish to answer this question	
Community attitudes to cannabis use in Western Australia Mobilising public support for providing needles to drug injectors: A pilot advocacy intervention		1997	Simon Lenton, Mike Phillips, Simon Lenton, Claudia Ovenden	N=400 Aged 17 and above Random sample of Western Australian population, from Perth, Bunbury and Geraldton Telephone survey Response rate: 38% Data were weighted by age of respondent	Do you think cannabis should be made as legal as alcohol? Yes No Unsure Do you believe that the possession of small amounts of cannabis for personal use should remain a criminal offence in Western Australia, that is, result in a criminal record and possibly a jail sentence if convicted? Yes No Unsure	
Preferences for policy options for cannabis in an Australian general population: A discrete choice experiment	International Journal of Drug Policy	2014	Marian Shanahan, Karen Gerard, Alison Ritter	N= Australian population Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) survey	Examines societal preferences for cannabis policies. Policy attributes which varied included legal status, health harms, criminal justice service costs, rates of cannabis use and purchase location.	A strong general preference for either civil penalties or legalisation compared to cannabis cautioning. There is a strong dislike of criminalising possession. Demographics and beliefs impact significantly on preferences.
The International Cannabis Cultivation Questionnaire (ICCCQ)				N>6000 Online survey Over 6000 cannabis cultivators from 11 countries completed our web survey		Internet-mediated research methods are increasingly used to access hidden populations It was more difficult to recruit cannabis cultivators in English-speaking countries. Growing practices were strikingly similar regardless of recruitment mode. Meaningful engagement with the target population improves data quality and quantity. Research participant anonymity is constrained by mass digital surveillance.